

Research Article

Field Trials of Botanical Extracts for Insect Pest Control on Mungbean (*Vigna radiata*) in Okigwe Southeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Field trials were conducted during the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons at Okigwe in Imo State Nigeria to evaluate the efficacy of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), *Occimum gratissimum*, *Chromolaena odorata*, and *Vernonia amygdalina* leaf extracts for the control of insect pests of mungbean variety NM-92. The experimental design was a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five treatments and four replications. Results obtained indicated that *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the population of *Chrysolagria* spp and *Megalurothrips sjostedti* when compared with the control in the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons. There was no significant difference in the population of *Zonocerus variegatus*, *Ootheca mutabilis*, *Maruca vitrata*, *Clavigralla tomentosicollis* and *Aphis craccivora*. *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* performed best in both dry pod weight and dry grain weight in both cropping seasons when compared with other treatments such as *Chromolaena odorata* and *Vernonia amygdalina* by recording a significantly higher dry pod weight and dry grain weight. *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* leaf extracts can be used to control *Chrysolagria* spp and *M. sjostedti* on mungbean applied at two weeks interval after crop emergence. The efficacy of the *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* in reducing the insect damage on the mungbean could be attributed to their respective active ingredients.

Keywords: Mungbean, *A. indica*, *O. gratissimum*, *V. amygdalina*, *O. odorata*, insect pest.

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Introduction

Mungbean, *Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek is a warm-season dicotyledonous pulse belonging to the order fabales and family fabaceae. It is widely cultivated in India, Thailand, Indonesia, and Philippines. The crop occupies an important place in the world food and nutrition economy (AVRDC, 2000). It is an important constituent in the diets of man and livestock in developing countries and constitutes a good source of protein

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which helps to supplement cereal diets, thus improving their nutritive value. They also provide substantial quantities of minerals, Iron, and Vitamins in diets (Weinberg, 2002).

Mungbean is widely consumed particularly in Asia and East Africa for the production of Mungbean sprout, a nutritious vegetable with as high as 38% protein (Osman, 1998; Sholar and Edward, 2001). The crop is often consumed as seed or in processed forms that include cold jellies, noodles, and cakes. Apart from boiling, it can also be fried or roasted before eating (Kay, 1999). Mungbean is reportedly used in traditional medicines for treating various ailments such as hepatitis, gastritis phytosterin that play an important role in promoting the physiological metabolism of human beings and animals (AVRDC, 2004). The plant as a whole serves as green manure or cover crop and hence helps immensely in improving the soil fertility through nodulation formation (Tiyagi and Alam, 1995).

Reports from the tropical regions clearly showed that some medicinal plant extracts such as Siam weed (*Chromolaena odorata*), Bitter leaf (*Vernonia amygdalina* Del), Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and Sweet basil *Occimum gratissimum* L products are reliable pesticides in terms of efficacy and as such are good substitutes for synthetic insecticides for field and storage insects and diseases (Kossou, 1989; Tanzubil, 1991). The potential of these plant materials was attributed to their various active ingredients some of which were inhibitory to the growth and development of insects. In some countries like Ghana and Burkina Faso leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica* and *Chromolaena odorata* have been reported to possess insecticidal properties and hence have been used effectively for insect pest control in cowpea and vegetable crops (Bottenberg and Singh, 1996),

In Nigeria, Mungbean is not widely cultivated. However, the cultivation of the crop is fast spreading to the humid rainforest agro-ecological zone of Nigeria (Mahmud *et al.*, 1986). Mungbean is prone to infestation by an array of insect pests such as leaf beetles (*Oothea mutabilis*, *Zonocerus variegatus*, *Chrysolgria* spp, Aphids, pod borers (*M. vitrata*), etc. which have been considered to be highly responsible for low yield of the crop in Nigeria and other countries where it is produced on a large scale (Mckinley, 1992). To sustain steady availability of this crop and on a large scale, adequate and environmentally safe control measures are necessary and hence this study aimed to evaluate the insecticidal potential of leaves of *Chromolaena odorata*, *Vernonia amygdalina* Del, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Occimum gratissimum* for the control of insect pest of Mungbean in Okigwe Southeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

The field experiments were conducted in the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons at the experimental site of the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) Mbato Okigwe Out-Station in Imo-State Nigeria.

The site is located in the humid rainforest zone of Nigeria and lies on latitude 05° 33' N and longitude 07° 23' E with an altitude of 130 meters above sea level. The mean temperature of the area varies between 27°C and 28°C with a mean and annual rainfall of 2048mm. The location is also associated with high relative humidity with average values ranging from 78% in February to 85% in July and September (Ortiz *et al.*, 1997). The medicinal plants used for the experiments were collected from Okigwe in Imo State and they include Sweet basil (*Occimum gratissimum*), Sian weed (*Chromolaena odorata*), Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and Bitter leaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*) and an untreated control which constitutes the five treatments. Land preparation for the experiments for the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons was done conventionally. There were twenty plots. The total land area was 16m x 12.5m or 0.02 ha with a plot size of 2m x 2m with 1.5m between plots and 2m within plants. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications.

Mungbean seeds variety NM-92 were obtained from the Research and Extension farm of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Umuahia, Abia State. Three seeds of the Mungbean were planted per hole at a seed rate of 40,000 seeds/ha on plots of 2m x 2m at a planting distance of 40cm x 20cm and a depth of 50cm.

One hundred grams (100gm) each of the dried leaves of *O. gratissimum*, *C. odorata*, *A. indica*, and *V. amygdalina* were weighed out using an electric weighing balance. Each of the various plant materials was then milled separately with a 2mm mesh sieve using a Thomas Ed-5 milling machine. Each plant material was bagged separately in polythene bags, labeled, and taken to the laboratory for extraction. The extraction was carried out at the Food Science Laboratory of Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

The milled plant materials were then soaked for 3 days in 10 ml of ethanol. The contents were stirred occasionally with a glass rod. The extraction was subsequently conducted in a 250ml Soxhlet extractor apparatus maintained at a temperature of 69°C using a heating mantle. The organic extract was stored in plastic vials and put in the refrigerator and ready for use. Each of the plant extract concentrate measured out at 75ml dosage was mixed with 5 litres of water and the spraying operation was done using a 5-liter capacity knapsack sprayer. Spraying was done at two weeks interval

after crop emergence until 12 weeks after planting (WAP). The control plots were not sprayed with the extracts.

Compound fertilizer N.P.K 20:10:10 at the rate of 200kg/ha was applied in two split doses. The first dose was given two weeks after plant establishment while the second dose was done two weeks after flowering. Weeding was done manually with hoes when the need arises.

Assessment of the population of the insects in the trials for the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons was done by visual counting on 10 randomly selected plants in the middle row of each plot. This was carefully done by gently examining the selected plants with careful observation of the leaves, pods, and stems for the correct assessment of the insects present on each plant. Sampling was done at 7-day intervals between 7 am – 8 pm when the insects were relatively inactive and easier to spot. For insects such as Pod borer (*M. vitrata*) and other pod sucking insects such as *C. tomentosicollis*, insect population and damage were assessed in the field by counting all bug species in the two middle rows of each plot and their numbers recorded. This was also done at the weekly interval at crop maturity. Data was also collected on the number of pods per plant, the weight of damaged/infested pods per plot, plant height, length of the pod, dry pod weight, and total dry grain yield.

Data obtained were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedure. Significant treatment means were separated using Least Significant Difference (LSD) at a 5% level of probability.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the study in 2018 (Table 1) showed that *Azadirachta indica* leaves (2.8) and *Occimum gratissimum* leaves (3.0) significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the population of *Chrysolagria* spp when compared with the control. Also *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* significantly ($P < 0.05$) controlled *M. sjostedti* population (1.52) and (2.32) respectively when compared with the other treatments. The treatments had no significant differences in controlling the population of *Zonocerus variegatus*, and *Aphis craccivora* on Mungbean.

The same trend of results was obtained in the study in 2019 where *Azadirachta indica* (3.1) and *Occimum gratissimum* (3.3) gave more promising results in terms of their efficacy in controlling the insect pests of Mungbean compared to the other plant materials (Table 2).

The treatments had no significant difference in some of the yield and yield-related parameters such as the number of pods per plant, plant height, and length of the pod as shown in Tables 3 and 4 for the 2018 and 2019 cropping seasons respectively. The results obtained from the yield (Tables 3 and 4) showed that *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* recorded a significant difference when compared with the control and recorded significantly higher dry pod weight (13.64kg/ha) and (12.03kg/ha) respectively and dry grain weight (12.61kg/ha) and (11.14kg/ha) respectively as well as reduced number of damaged pods in 2018. The result followed the same trend in the 2019 cropping season as shown in Table 4. This is similar to the work of Asawalam and Osondu (2012) where they recorded a significantly higher grain yield in cowpea plant *Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp using medicinal plant leaf extracts like *Cucuma longa*, *Occimum gratissimum* *Chromolaena odorata*, etc to control insect pests on Cowpea.

The plant extracts of *A. indica* and *O. gratissimum* provided the greatest protection of the mungbean in the field against the infestation by *Chrysolagria* spp and *Megalurothrips sjostedti*. The efficacy of the *A. indica* leaves on these insects could be attributed to the presence of Azadirachtin which is the active constituent of the *A. indica* plant. The same could be attributed to *O. gratissimum* which also is efficacious due to its repellent activity on stored product insects (Hassanali *et al.*, 1990). However, this observation is in agreement with earlier studies by Ibekwe *et al.* (2015) where promising results in terms of reduced insect infestation/damage and the increased yield of watermelon using some medicinal plant leaf extracts were obtained.

Table 1: Effect of different plant extracts on Insect population in Mungbean during the 2018 cropping season in Okigwe.

Treatment	<i>Chrysologria</i> spp	<i>Zonocerus</i> <i>variegatus</i>	<i>Ootheca</i> <i>mutabilis</i>	<i>Maruca</i> <i>vitrata</i>	<i>Clarigralla</i> <i>tomentosicollis</i>	<i>Megelothrps</i> <i>sjostedti</i>	<i>Aphis</i> <i>craccivora</i>
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	3.0	0.29	0.39	0.52	1.30	2.32	0.23
<i>C. odorata</i>	5.3	0.14	0.36	0.63	2.12	8.41	0.34
<i>A. Indica</i>	2.8	0.27	0.43	0.41	1.32	1.52	0.16
<i>V. amygdalina</i>	6.2	0.28	0.41	0.48	2.33	8.10	0.36
Control	11.4	0.21	0.35	0.56	2.41.	8.67	1.21
LSD	0.9	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.31	NS

Table 2: Effect of different plant extracts on Insect population in Mungbean during the 2019 cropping season in Okigwe.

Treatment	<i>Chrysologria</i> spp	<i>Zonocerus</i> <i>variegatus</i>	<i>Ootheca</i> <i>mutabilis</i>	<i>Maruca</i> <i>vitrata</i>	<i>Clarigralla</i> <i>tomentosicollis</i>	<i>Megelothrps</i> <i>sjostedti</i>	<i>Aphis</i> <i>craccivora</i>
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	3.3	1.04	0.31	0.43	1.36	2.36	0.38
<i>C. odorata</i>	5.8	1.21	0.36	0.58	2.18	9.02	0.42
<i>A. indica</i>	3.1	0.29	0.27	0.37	1.30	2.14	0.18
<i>V. amygdalina</i>	7.2	0.24	0.41	0.46	2.29	8.89	0.43
Control	13.1	1.55	0.44	0.53	2.63.	9.30	1.26
LSD	1.02	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.43	NS

Table 3: Effect of different plant extracts on Insect on damage and yield-related parameters in Mungbean infested with insects during the 2018 cropping season in Okigwe.

Treatment	No of pods per plant	Plant height (cm)	Length of pod (cm)	No of damaged /infested pods	Dry pod weight (Kg/ha)	Dry grain weight (kg/ha)
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	10.8	21.6	9.4	1.28	12.03	11.14
<i>C. odorata</i>	10.3	20.7	9.6	3.10	7.20	8.31
<i>A. indica</i>	11.6	22.3	9.7	1.51	13.64	12.61
<i>V. amygdalina</i>	9.8	21.5	9.4	3.26	7.73	5.24
Control	9.2	20.7	9.2	8.23	6.12.	4.56
LSD	NS	NS	NS	6,37	6.31	4.89

Table 4: Effect of different plant extracts on Insect damage and yield-related parameters in Mungbean infested with insects during the 2019 cropping season in Okigwe.

Treatment	No of pods per plant	Plant height cm	Length of pod (cm)	No of damaged /infested pods	Dry pod weight Kg/ha)	Dry grain weight (kg/ha)
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	11.3	23.2	9.3	1.30	12.09	12.10
<i>C. odorata</i>	11.1	21.6	9.6	3.62	7.25	8.22
<i>A. indica</i>	12.6	23.8	9.8	1.21	13.34	12.42
<i>V. amygdalina</i>	10.3	22.4	9.3	3.53	7.10	5.36
Control	9.0	21.0	9.2	8.30.	6.93.	4.73
LSD	NS	NS	NS	6.24	7.10	4.13

Conclusion

The study revealed that the medicinal plant leaf extracts were efficacious in the reduction of insect infestation and increased the yield of the Mungbean compared with the control. There is a need for further investigation/research studies on new extracts that might be pursued in the future to improve the results obtained in this present study. This could give better results of not only suppressing the insect population but will also go a long way toward achieving higher yields.

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